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CURRENT ASPECTS OF THE USE OF GREEN ENERGY RESOURCES IN THE CONTEXT OF POST-CONFLICT TERRITORIES AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT PRINCIPLES IN AZERBAIJAN

Aliyev Sh.

doctor of economic sciences, professor of Sumgait State University.

Head of the Centre For Karabakh Economic Research UNEC –

Azerbaijan State Economic University –

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4997-7563>

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Abstract

The current aspects of the use of green energy resources in the context of post-conflict areas and sustainable development principles in Azerbaijan were examined. The problems of strengthening the country's energy security were explained. Priorities for increasing the share of green energy in the energy production structure were given. The economic efficiency of creating green energy infrastructure in post-conflict areas was substantiated. The importance of expanding green energy projects was noted. The existing potential of green energy in Azerbaijan was assessed. Targets were given for the efficient use of wind and solar energy. Proposals were given to ensure the efficient use of green energy resources in Azerbaijan in the near future.

Keywords: Azerbaijan, green energy, sustainable development, sustainable development principles, post-conflict areas, green energy infrastructure.

It should be noted that in modern times, the green energy paradigm is coming to the fore in the world as one of the means of solving environmental problems. This industry involves the use of alternative energy sources (sun, water, wind, etc.) in various fields of human activity. Currently, the topic of resource conservation and ecology is widely discussed and is reflected in the works of various scientists. The term “green energy” is widely spread not only in the scientific community, but also in the media. This topic has intensively risen to the maximum level of relevance by being included in international, national programs and conferences. We believe that sustainable development is a concept put forward on how to build the future world in order not to disrupt the development of the new (future) generation in the current conditions. The world is increasingly paying attention to climate and environmental risks, modification of tools and infrastructure for sustainable development. The use of green economy in this concept is a tool that combines unique methods and means by which the desired economic result can be achieved [1].

It is known that for the first time the term “green energy” began to take shape and spread widely in the United States in 1978 with the signing of a law promoting the use and development of renewable energy sources. Green energy is a term that means energy production technologies that do not pollute the environment (harmful emissions, greenhouse gases). The growth of the world's population leads to an increase in electricity consumption. Every year, people rely more and more on technology, they cannot imagine a day without it. However, the development of technologies does not stand still, they become more compact and are very demanding on the quality of electricity. As a result, electricity consumption is becoming more and more and continues to grow. The main possible solution to this problem is the acquisition

of green energy sources [2]. On the other hand, green energy is the type of energy that most fully meets the interests of society as a whole. It is characterized, first of all, by low emissions of carbon compounds. In the economy of a country where green energy is at the forefront, a large number of private and public investments are directed to various activities, the main purpose of which is primarily related to: increasing the efficiency of using natural resources; reducing negative factors that directly affect the decline of biodiversity; reducing emissions of harmful substances into the atmosphere, which ultimately leads to global pollution of all nature; partial restoration of natural capital [3]. As civilization develops and the world population increases, as production capacities increase, there is a greater demand for fuel resources, and these are considered one of the most complex problems of the modern era. Thus, the main sources of fuel resources currently used are exhaustible sources, and these resources are also unevenly distributed in the world. Most countries in the world are deprived of access to important energy resources, and the struggle for energy is increasingly global in nature [4].

It is no coincidence that in the context of global challenges, energy security and energy supply issues occupy a central place. But is there a solution to these problems? Or, are the elements of the “green” economy, including green energy, which have been in intensive circulation in recent times, capable of solving these problems? We are witnessing the complexity of global problems considered in countries around the world and at the level of international organizations. For example, problems related to climate change are becoming more complex every year, or the efficient organization of the exchange of energy resources, including the active introduction of green energy to world markets, are becoming a priority. It is commendable that Azerbaijan, which has been

strengthening its status as a strategic partner in Europe's energy security year after year, is taking important steps to export its hydrocarbon resources to European countries experiencing problems with energy supply. At the same time, along with natural gas raw materials, the issues of producing other alternative energy resources and exporting them to the European market, which is in high demand, are also of serious importance. Strengthening the "green" economy and increasing the production of green energy play an important role in solving many problems, including environmental problems and resource shortages. Along with this, it allows reducing the negative impacts of human activity and intervention on the environment. It reduces atmospheric pollution and forms sources of energy resources that are more harmless to nature and people. According to the Memorandum of Understanding signed between Azerbaijan and the European Commission, by 2027, natural gas exports to Europe will increase by 2 times and will reach 20 billion cubic meters. Azerbaijan, not content with natural gas extracted from the ground alone, objectively assesses its green energy potential and is continuously working on this. The green energy potential obtained from wind in the Azerbaijani part of the Caspian Sea is 157 gigawatts. In addition, there are an additional 27 gigawatts of green energy potential in the land areas of our country. According to the agreement signed with the United Arab Emirates' Masdar company, wind and solar energy production in our country will reach 4 gigawatts by 2027 and 6 gigawatts by 2037. An agreement has already been signed to lay an underwater cable line from Azerbaijan to Europe, that is, through Georgia, to Romania, and the transmission capacity of that line is at the level of 4 gigawatts. Another significant event is that, according to the Memorandum of Understanding signed with the Australian company Fortescue Future Industries, targeted investments will be directed to increase green energy production in Azerbaijan to 12 gigawatts. In general, based on the agreements and memorandums signed to date, the production and export of 25 gigawatts of green energy in Azerbaijan to world markets may be realized in the near future. Thus, the production and export opportunities of green energy in Azerbaijan will increase significantly, and our country will further increase its competitiveness and image as a reliable energy supply partner. Economic construction in Karabakh is currently underway intensively. On the other hand, it is known that there are serious resources for the development of the Karabakh economy [5].

It should be noted that Azerbaijan has already gone down in history as one of the rare countries that has restored and revived the liberated territories at the expense of its financial strength and economic power. We believe that the main goal of organizing the "Green Energy Zone" in Karabakh is to create renewable energy sources and, in general, to take targeted measures to reduce carbon dioxide emissions in our country. By the decree of the Head of State dated May 3, 2021, measures are envisaged to create a "green energy" zone in the liberated territories. Energy projects implemented in a complex and systematic manner in these territories will be of strategic

importance in creating an exemplary and efficient "green energy" space in Azerbaijan in the near future. These factors will also give a significant impetus to the development of the non-oil sector of our country, and it should be noted that our state has also developed and implemented stimulating tax mechanisms in these areas [6]. The essence of the "green energy" approach adopted in Azerbaijan is that, on the one hand, energy will increasingly come from renewable sources, and on the other hand, our energy savings are more efficient than producing the same amount of energy. As part of the "green growth" concept, a policy is being implemented in Azerbaijan to transform the Karabakh and East Zangezur regions into "green energy" zones [7]. Another important issue is the historical work that Azerbaijan has begun to transition to a new socio-economic development model based on the principles of green energy and a green economy. These factors, in addition to strengthening the economic security of our country, form additional potential for significantly increasing its important component, energy security [8].

One of the main directions in the National Priorities for Socio-Economic Development until 2030 is the formation of a "Country of Clean Environment and Green Growth". Taking these into account, 2024 was declared the "Year of Solidarity for a Green World" by the Decree of the Head of State. Another historic and important issue is the high-level organization of the next Session of the Conference of the Parties to the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change (COP-29) in Azerbaijan in November 2024. By hosting such an internationally prestigious event, Azerbaijan has significantly increased its international image and competitiveness. This will also give an additional impetus to the development of green energy, and the development of green energy is of strategic importance in the state's security system. The construction of modern cities and villages based on "smart" technologies in the Karabakh economic region, the intensive implementation of the First State Program on the Great Return, and the creation of a "green" energy zone at the same time have a multiplicative effect on the development of the region. Similar development processes are shaping a new progressive and modern model of regional development in our country [9].

Environmental problems are becoming acute worldwide. The problems caused by climate change make it difficult to provide essential food products. Land areas are being flooded or are being lost due to drought. In addition, in order to ensure sustainable development, it is necessary to save resources and take into account the needs of future generations. For this, the development of green energy sectors and the establishment of green economy principles are necessary. In such a situation, Azerbaijan, while sharing its oil and gas resources with countries around the world, primarily the European Union countries, attaches strategic importance to the creation of renewable energy sources. As we mentioned earlier, the renewable energy potential in Azerbaijan is 135 GW on land and 157 GW at sea. Also, the wind energy potential is 3,000 MW, and the solar energy potential is

23,000 MW. On the other hand, of the 8.3 thousand MW of electricity currently produced in our country, 1.7 thousand MW is due to the power of hydroelectric power plants. This is a 20% share. The expansion of the network of hydroelectric power plants in the liberated territories will allow increasing the share of green energy. Currently, an action plan is being implemented to create a green energy zone in the liberated territories in 2022-2026. In the context of these factors, it should be taken into account that approximately 25% of Azerbaijan's internal water resources are in the liberated territories. Therefore, new opportunities have been formed for the efficient use of water resources.

After the Great Karabakh Victory, the processes of creating infrastructure and forming fundamental foundations for socio-economic development in the liberated territories are accelerating [10]. Conceptual approaches and priorities in this direction have been almost completely determined. The head of state's consistent visits to the liberated territories and his on-site acquaintance with the revival measures carried out generally provide a strong impetus and additional incentives to the socio-economic development of the newly created Karabakh economic region. Among the successfully implemented projects, the creation of energy infrastructure and the uninterrupted and reliable supply of the liberated territories with electricity are noteworthy. In a short period of time, the construction of 110 kW electricity lines in the directions of Shukurbayli - Shusha (75 km), Shukurbayli - Zangilan (110 km), Khindiristan - Agdam (35 km) was completed.

It should be noted that a powerful electricity network was formed in the Karabakh region during the Soviet Union, and 10 electricity networks operated here. The hated enemy completely destroyed or plundered this infrastructure during the occupation. In the current reality, the presence of strong energy sources in the region and the fact that it attracts attention with its great potential give grounds to say that a new energy infrastructure and network based on more modern technologies will soon be created in Karabakh. If we look at the resource possibilities for this, we will see that there is a prospect of creating a network of hydroelectric power stations on the basis of the rivers Tartar, Bazarchay, Hakari, etc. Work is already being intensified in this direction, and the work of some previously operating hydroelectric power stations has been restored. Thus, the restored 20 MW hydroelectric power station in Sugovushan was put into operation ("Sugovushan-1" and "Sugovushan-2"), etc.

In modern times, Azerbaijan is experiencing its own dynamic development as an independent state and has become a strong country where global initiatives are taking shape. Based on the initial results of COP29, we can note that it is possible to make serious contributions to solving complex problems that concern the peoples and states of the world. However, for this, it is important to unite the efforts of the world's states and use them effectively to take more effective measures. At COP29, the consolidation of important financial resources required to eliminate the negative consequences of global climate change has acquired strategic importance. The issues of establishing

specialized institutions for climate finance, preparing investment and financial mechanisms, assuming obligations by states on green energy, especially accepting obligations related to the maintenance of green energy, have become quite relevant.

It should be noted that the transformation taking place in the development processes of the global economy determines new trends and development impulses in modern conditions [11]. The issues of building a green energy infrastructure are of exceptional importance, and in this regard, taking into account the need to create an appropriate infrastructure based on the basic principles of sustainable development, special attention is paid to the efficient use of energy resources. Thus, the negative consequences of complex processes and global problems in ensuring the energy security of countries around the world are increasing. Problems in these areas are becoming more complex every year, and the negative consequences of climate change are increasing. At the same time, there are difficulties in the rational distribution of energy resources, therefore, the task of ensuring the production of green energy and its entry into the world market is of the highest priority. Based on the priority of ensuring green energy, the issues of forming a green economy, creating an efficient structure of the economy, and improving existing economic mechanisms are becoming increasingly relevant. Among such problems and issues, the need to solve problems of economical and productive use of resource potential, and intensify the transfer of high technologies, especially waste-free technologies, are more noticeable [12]. In this regard, there is a serious need for fundamental research, synthesis, comparison, and generalization of such issues. In addition, there is a serious need to accelerate the establishment of a green energy structure and ensure the efficiency of the mechanisms applied in this direction. We would also like to draw attention to the issues of forecasting world population growth by 2050. On the other hand, since energy resources are unevenly distributed between regions and countries of the world, additional difficulties, problems, conflicts, etc. arise. Against this background, energy security problems are rapidly increasing and diversification of energy sources is required. It is this factor that makes it more necessary to intensify the development of the green economy and, first of all, the creation of the necessary high-tech green energy infrastructure, which requires large investments.

In our opinion, the countries of the world should make greater efforts and take the necessary measures to solve global energy problems. They should ensure the creation of more economical regimes (mechanisms) of using natural resources and non-renewable energy resources. It is necessary to deepen the processes of transfer and application of high technologies between countries and ensure the development of effective mechanisms for the efficient use of energy resources [13]. We believe that despite the intensity of the creation and implementation of green energy infrastructure, the ecological situation in the world is worsening from year to year. This factor clearly shows the importance of the transition of countries around the

world to a green economy and especially green energy. It is in the context of the above-mentioned problems that more intensive measures are being taken in most countries of the world to improve the concept of a green economy and create a green energy infrastructure.

In our opinion, against the background of these problems, factors arising from the concept of sustainable development come to the fore. First of all, the issues of economical use of resources, taking into account the needs of future generations for these resources, the development and application of more efficient regulatory mechanisms and incentives for existing mechanisms have risen to a strategic level. In addition, there are tendencies for countries around the world to seek alternative ways to ensure energy security. In such a case, bringing the problems of greening the economy and efficiency to the agenda, conducting in-depth scientific research in the direction of creating and implementing new progressive models of the economic regime are considered an inevitable process [14]. At the same time, achieving the effective application of the results of scientific research in various segments of the economy is of great importance. Let us note that in the conditions of increasing economic demand in the modern era, the productive use of green energy sources is of great importance. In recent decades, humanity has become more aware that the burning of fossil fuels such as coal, oil and natural gas has caused large-scale global problems that have become uncontrollable. We have specifically distinguished a group of issues related to these:

Modern energy sources are obtained from depleted natural resources. It is understood that in the relatively near future there will be a shortage of natural resources, as a result of which future generations will face difficulties in energy production and ensuring the viability of the population. As a result of the active development of energy, the problem of environmental pollution is becoming more and more acute. However, green energy minimizes damage to the environment and thereby reduces the negative consequences of the global problem. The cost of current non-renewable energy resources is constantly changing, creating difficulties in the world and the global economy. However, green energy can help maintain stable prices, since after the initial costs associated with the creation of a renewable energy source, the costs of maintaining and operating this source are often lower than those of using fossil fuels.

On the other hand, green energy can act as a catalyst for energy security, sustainable development, and social, technological, and industrial innovations in a country. Increasing the consumption of green energy has a positive effect on its economic and social development. Moreover, since energy plays an important role in industrial and technological development, the supply and use of cheap, clean fuel is of particular importance for global stability in the world [15]. In this regard, there is a need to use renewable energy sources that can have a positive impact on all spheres of life, including the stable development of national economies. In our opinion, the development of green energy in the economic sphere can have a

positive impact on solving a group of issues: 1. Increasing the number of jobs and alleviating the employment problem. 2. Reducing consumer spending and creating more resources. 3. Eliminating dependence on fossil fuels imported from other countries and 4. Green energy is not only a solution to global problems, but also a means of stimulating the economic activity of entrepreneurs, business entities and the population.

Along with this, we believe that it is logical to create an environmentally friendly, that is, green energy potential that will help solve the problem of environmental pollution. These facts help stimulate the areas of sales and consumption. "Until a green energy source is created that can fully meet the demand for electricity, even if humanity realizes that it causes irreparable damage to the environment, it will not be able to stop burning fossil fuels" [16]. Currently, researchers and experts are increasingly engaged in the study and development of mechanisms for the formation of new clean and sustainable energy sources, which means that fossil fuels will soon be replaced by a more environmentally friendly resource. It should be noted that Azerbaijan has committed to reducing greenhouse gas emissions by 40% by 2050. In addition, it is planned to increase the share of renewable energy in the structure of total energy resources to 30% by 2030. Azerbaijan has made serious and long-term commitments to implement the necessary measures to ensure a 1.5°C temperature limit in the global context. Azerbaijan is implementing permanent and consistent measures in these conceptual directions [17].

In addition, Azerbaijan plans to increase the volume of natural gas exported to the European market to 20 billion m³ by 2027. At the same time, the creation of infrastructure for alternative energy sources has begun in various regions of the country. In 2037, 6 GW of renewable energy can be produced. President Ilham Aliyev noted at the opening ceremony of the COP29 Leaders' Summit: "Now I would like to say a few words about Azerbaijan's Green Agenda. Our technical potential in renewable energy is 135 gigawatts onshore and 157 gigawatts offshore. Last year, the UAE's Masdar company inaugurated a 230-megawatt solar power plant in one of our regions. Saudi Arabia's Acwa Power is currently building a 240-megawatt wind power plant. Within the framework of COP29, an agreement will be signed with the United Kingdom's BP company on the construction of a 240-megawatt solar power plant in the Jabrayil region, which was liberated from Armenian occupation four years ago. Thanks to this project, decarbonization will be ensured at the Sangachal terminal, one of the largest oil and gas terminals in the world. We are also focusing on export markets and are actively working with our partners to implement another important energy security project, which involves laying an energy cable from the Caspian Sea to the bottom of the Black Sea. This will allow us to export green energy to Europe, and the technical potential of this cable is four gigawatts. By the way, the feasibility study will be completed soon. "But still, this is just the beginning [18].

At the same time, Azerbaijan will implement joint projects with Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan to create

green energy infrastructure. Azerbaijan, together with a group of world countries, has increased its activity in developing financial mechanisms for green energy projects. Another important issue is related to the formation of a green economy structure and the creation of green energy infrastructure in the processes of revitalizing post-conflict territories. "The newly created Karabakh and East Zangezur economic regions have great resources in terms of forming and increasing green energy potential" [19]. Development projects for the Karabakh and East Zangezur economic regions mainly cover priorities until 2040. In particular, taking into account the current issues arising from the tasks of the First State Program on the return of internally displaced persons to their native lands, the prospects for forming and increasing green energy potential in these economic regions are becoming increasingly attractive. The liberated territories have been declared green energy zones in general and a targeted action program has been formed in this regard. Green energy projects will make a significant contribution to improving the structure of energy resource production in our country. On the other hand, in a context of increasing modern global threats, the development of green energy is characterized as one of the highest priority tasks of the country's national and economic security.

In addition to the above, we believe that in the near future, more intensive development of green energy infrastructure will be ensured in post-conflict areas. In addition, in order to implement the priority tasks of the transition to green energy in Azerbaijan in the context of sustainable development and prepare effective mechanisms for action, we consider it important to seriously consider a group of factors:

- First of all, the green energy potential of the region should be studied in more depth, and the reserves should be objectively assessed;

- There is a need to accelerate the processes of creating green energy infrastructure in the economic region, this factor is of serious importance in settlement, creation of new jobs and realization of the Great Return;

- Launching targeted scientific research at Karabakh University to ensure the efficient use of the region's green energy resources;

- In order to intensify green energy infrastructure in the Karabakh economic region, it is necessary to use the experience of more developed countries and companies in this field in the world, and comprehensive measures should be taken in this regard, etc.

- It is important to expand the scale of the investment projects launched to create a large and promising green energy infrastructure and to implement projects aimed at creating a similar infrastructure in all regions of the country;

- A thorough study of the green energy potential in the Karabakh economic region, an optimal assessment of resources and related reserves should be ensured;

- There is a need to develop a separate action strategy and, more precisely, a state program for the efficient use of water resources, small rivers, and

especially rivers with water all year round, in the Karabakh economic region, and in this regard, it is advisable to prepare and implement a special state program for the expansion of the network of hydroelectric power plants in the Karabakh economic region for the period up to 2030;

- In order to more effectively organize the processes of implementing the green energy concept in our country, we propose to improve management mechanisms and create a specialized "Green Energy Corporation" that meets international requirements, etc.

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